

Interactions in Aqueous Solutions†

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THE stability of the native structure of proteins and conformation of other biopolymers in aqueous solution which are of fundamental importance for many biological phenomena has been the subject of great challenge and extensive investigations¹⁻⁹. It has been observed that conformation transitions are extremely sensitive to the subtle changes in the solvent medium, reflecting thereby their dependence on the hydration states of biopolymers and soluble small molecular species involved. It is now recognised that water plays an important role in the conformation of biopolymers^{9,10}. This is due to the uniqueness of water¹⁰⁻¹² as the universal solvent, the fact which is still not generally appreciated. Water does not conform to generalised claims or predictions based on experiments performed with other solvents. None of the accepted theories of polymer solutions is able to explain the highly specific conformation of protein. The understanding of hydration behaviour of a solute is linked with the knowledge about water structure. In spite of extensive efforts directed towards the study of water structure, the description of water structure is still a matter of conjecture. In fact, a large number of views are available in literature. A brief account of the present status of knowledge about water structure is, therefore, described here.

Structure of liquid water :

The uniqueness of water¹⁰⁻¹² among liquids is evident from its anomalous physicochemical properties usually not found in other liquids.

In spite of enormous investment in terms of experimental and theoretical studies to explore the water structure, a compact, useful description is yet to be seen. The situation is nicely reflected through different contradictory views presented in a large number of articles and books¹⁰⁻²⁶. Most of the models²⁷ put forth are limited in scope because of their treatment of only some of the observed features of water. At the most, they give partial description of what water may be like²⁷. Even the computer simulation studies by Monte Carlo method²⁸⁻³¹ and by molecular dynamics method by Stillinger and coworkers³²⁻³⁴ do not come out with an unequivocal view of water structure. Its results have been used both by mixture-model and continuum-model protagonists in support of their viewpoint³⁵.

Hydration behaviour of various solutes :

The precise understanding of the hydration behaviour of a solute requires the knowledge of the

mechanism by which an introduction of a solute molecule perturbs the structure of water. On a molecular level, the structure of water is described in terms of a molecular pair correlation function $g(r, \Omega)$, where r is the distance between the centres of mass of the two molecules and Ω expresses the orientation contribution. So the perturbation due to a single solute particle is needed to be examined in terms of changes in $g_{ww}(r)$, where w refers to a water molecule and also in terms of $g_{sw}(r, \Omega)$, the solute-water pair correlation function. Though some progress has been made, as little is yet known regarding $U(r_{ij})$ and $g(r_{ij})$ in pure liquid. Until further progress is made in the theories of liquids, semi-empirical approach will have to serve. Valuable information can be obtained from systematic studies of solute-water, solute-solute and water-water interactions in dilute solutions of electrolytes, non-electrolytes and polyfunctional hydrophilic moieties³⁶. The structural changes brought about by a solute can be rationalised in terms of 'flickering cluster' model³⁷ (Fig. 1) of water; in which water molecules are considered to be in dynamic equilibrium between the bulky tetrahedrally hydrogen

Fig. 1. Frank—Wen flickering cluster model of liquid water (Ref. 37).

bonded clusters and the denser molecules represented as

If a solute causes a shift so as to increase the number and average half-life of clusters, it is termed

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as a 'structure-maker', if it effects in the opposite direction, is called a 'structure-breaker'⁸⁸. This model has been very useful in discussing the effects of solutes on water structure⁸⁹. These effects can be detected experimentally by observing the changes brought about by the solutes in the properties of water, such as fluidity (reorientation time, viscosity, conductance *etc.*) and heat capacity. For instance, structure-makers are shown to decrease the fluidity of water (by causing increase in reorientation time and increase in viscosity) and result in positive excess partial molar heat capacity in water. The reverse is true for structure-breakers.

Hydration interactions are classified on the basis of different chemical types of molecular and ionic hydration sites. Three distinct types of hydration behaviour commonly used, ionic hydration, hydrophobic hydration and specific molecular hydration — are discussed briefly.

Ionic hydration: An ion when introduced into water, interferes with the local ordering of the water molecules in its neighborhood and tends to impose a new order on them. Many studies show that simple electrolytes with high charge-density, such as LiF and MgCl₂, can be categorised as net structure-makers and salts with low charge-density, like CsI and KBr, as net structure-breakers. Frank and Wen⁸⁸, in order to explain such observations, have put forth a working hypothesis, which enjoys the support of many experimental studies. According to them, an ion in aqueous solution can be visualised (Fig. 2) as surrounded by three concentric regions, (i) an innermost structure-forming region (A) of polarised, immobilised and electrostricted water molecules, (ii) an intermediate structure-broken region (B) in which the water is less ice-like, *i.e.* more random in organisation than ordinary water, and (iii) an outer region (C) containing water having the normal liquid structure.

Fig. 2. Frank—Wen multizone model of ion-hydration in aqueous solutions (Ref. 88).

Ions with low charge-density have relatively weak electrostatic fields which makes the region (A) very small, thereby causing net decrease in structure. In the case of structure-making ions of high charge-density, the region (A) of immobilisation exceeds

region (B), which results in a net structural increase around these ions.

Various experimental techniques have been employed to study spectroscopic⁴⁰⁻⁴⁸, transport⁴⁴, dielectric⁴⁵ and thermodynamic⁴⁶ behaviour of ionic solutions. Friedman and Krishnan⁴⁸ from their thermodynamic studies, conclude that the electrostatic model (which considers solvent as a dielectric continuum) is inadequate to describe ionic solutions. They have proposed a model for aqueous ionic solutions, based on ideas given by Frank and Evans⁴⁷, Gurney⁴⁹, and Samoilov¹⁵. They assume that around each solute particle X^Z (Z = charge of the ion), there is a region termed as co-sphere, having the thickness of one solvent molecule in which the solvent properties are affected by the presence of the solute and these effects are characterised by the thermodynamics of the process,

$$n[\text{solvent}(\text{pure bulk liquid})] - n[\text{solvent in co-sphere state next to X}^Z]$$

where, n = number of solvent molecules in the co-sphere.

While the Frank and Wen⁸⁸ model and more recent, Ben-Naim-Stillinger⁴⁹ model of ionic solutions are rather qualitative and are supported by the considerations of kinetic properties or the way the solutions scatter X-rays or neutrons⁵⁰, the Friedman—Krishnan model emphasises on the contributions of the various co-sphere states to the thermodynamic properties of solutions.

Computer simulation studies^{51,52} on aqueous electrolyte solutions have confirmed the presence of two types of hydration shells, *viz.* the inner hydration shell with a well defined hydration number (ions with low charge densities are exceptions) and outer hydration shell where water-water correlation depicts a decrease in 'structure'.

Hydrophobic hydration: The relatively low solubility of non-polar compounds in water has been known for a long time. This low solubility has been considered⁵³ to be linked with the large decrease in entropy which makes the free energy of their solution positive, in spite of their exothermic dissolution in water. This gives such aqueous solutions a status different from the normal liquid mixtures in which the solubility is determined by enthalpic factors. Thus the entropy of transfer of a non-polar compound or noble gas from an organic solvent to aqueous is found to have a large negative value which decreases as the temperature is increased, so that $\bar{C}_{p,s}^{\circ} (= TdS_g^{\circ}/dT)$ has large positive values^{57,58}. The large entropy decreases, resulting from addition of non-polar groups to water, indicate a small number of configurational states for a given energy, which means that packing of water molecules around dissolved group is somewhat tighter than in pure water, a situation generally called 'structure increase'⁵⁴.

Frank and Wen⁸⁸ have explained this water structure stabilisation in terms of the relative

incapability of such solutes in producing of transmitting the cluster disruptive influence, on account of the relative feebleness of their polarisability and of the electrostatic influences into which they can enter. An 'ice-like' patch (not necessarily resembling ice in its configurational states) should be able to form more readily in a volume element bound by the non-polar solute molecule, and once formed should have a larger half-life by virtue of having a part of its boundary protected from the high energy attack which tries to dissolve it. This enhancement of structure in aqueous solutions of non-polar solutes in comparison to pure water, has been termed as iceberg formation or hydration of second kind or hydrophobic hydration. The reverse process of hydrophobic hydration, that is, the creation of solute-solute contact, is called hydrophobic interaction^{1, 57, 58-59}. The latter process is spontaneous with $\Delta S > 0$ and $\Delta G < 0$ ^{57, 58}. Both hydrophobic hydration and hydrophobic interaction are pictorially described⁵⁶ in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Diagrammatic representation of (a) hydrophobic hydration and (b)-(e) hydrophobic interactions, (b) Kauzmann-Nemethy-Scheraga contact interaction, (c) globular protein folding, (d) proposed solvent-separated interaction, and (e) possible stabilisation of helix by interaction as in (d) (Ref. 56).

Direct evidence for the formation of iceberg or cages around solutes containing non-polar groups is not available. However, the existence of solid gas hydrates⁶⁰⁻⁶² and clathrates⁶³ does provide indirect support to iceberg formation.

Specific molecular hydration : Interactions which predominate in solutions of polyfunctional solutes

are of rather different nature from those which give rise to the typical hydrophobic behaviour. The hydration effects in solutions of non-polar and predominantly apolar solutes have been shown to be largely non-specific and are characterised by micro-heterogeneities (reflected in marked concentration dependence of physical properties of these solutes). The opposite is the case for highly polar solutes. In the latter solutes, one is concerned with specific interactions between proton donor or acceptor sites (e.g. $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{N}-$, $-\text{O}$, $-\text{C}=\text{O}$) on neutral molecules and water molecules. Reconciliation of these interactions with three-dimensional order in liquid water is also an important factor.

Recently, Tait and coworkers⁶⁴ have proposed the specific hydration model which emphasises that in addition to the number of potential hydration sites, hydration interactions depend on relative distance between, and mutual orientations of these hydration sites. Since the hydration interaction competes with the inter-molecular hydrogen bonding in water, solute molecules which are able to interact with the solvent without major perturbations in the solvent structure are likely to interact preferentially.

Investigation of thermodynamic properties :

Since the thermodynamic parameters, such as integral enthalpy of solution at infinite dilution (ΔH_s°), limiting heat capacity of dissolution (ΔC_p°), limiting partial molar heat capacity¹⁻⁶ ($\bar{C}_{p,1}^\circ$) and limiting partial molar volume^{1, 65, 66} (\bar{V}_1°) are sensitive to the arrangement of the solvent molecules around a solute molecule, they offer one of the better methods to obtain information on solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions.

Much of the earlier work had been done in concentrated solutions and extrapolation to infinite dilution gave rise to incorrect values of limiting thermodynamic quantities and limiting concentration dependence. Unfortunately, complete reliance in the past has been placed on ΔH_s° , ΔS_s° and ΔC_p° derived indirectly from solubility data as a function of temperature. van't Hoff enthalpies derived from solubility data on sparingly soluble substances, are subject to such large errors that differentiation of such results is largely meaningless. More sophisticated and sensitive experimental techniques have now become available. We have used these in our laboratory to obtain precise and accurate thermodynamic parameters at very low concentrations (10^{-3} - 10^{-4} molal) so that the results reflect only the solute-solvent interactions.

Instruments and operational procedure :

The integral enthalpies of solution (ΔH_s) were determined calorimetrically using an isoperibol solution calorimeter. Since the measurements are made in very dilute solutions of the solute (10^{-3} - 10^{-4} molal), the ΔH_s is either independent of concentration or the concentration effect is masked by the experimental error; the enthalpy of solution at infinite dilution, (ΔH_s°) was obtained by averaging

the values of ΔH_s . The uncertainty in the values is expressed as 95% confidence limits.

The limiting heat capacity of dissolution, ΔC_p^0 , was derived as follows from the ΔH_s^0 values using integral heat method,

$$\Delta C_p^0 = \frac{d\Delta H_s^0}{dT}$$

where, dT is small interval of temperature.

Partial molar heat capacity, \bar{C}_p^0 , was either derived from ΔC_p^0 using the relation,

$$\bar{C}_p^0 = \Delta C_p^0 + \bar{C}_p^*$$

where \bar{C}_p^* is the heat capacity of pure solute, or by fitting apparent molar heat capacity (ϕC_p) data using least-squares method. The apparent molar heat capacities (ϕC_p) of the solutes were obtained from the measurements of specific heat capacities of solution using Picker micro-flow calorimeter,

$$\phi C_p = MC_p - (C_p - \bar{C}_p^*)/M$$

where, C_p is the specific heat capacity of the solution, \bar{C}_p^* is the specific heat capacity of water, and m is the molality of the solution.

Partial molar volume of the solutes at infinite dilution, \bar{V}_s^0 , were obtained by extrapolating densimetrically - determined apparent molar volume values, to infinite dilution. The apparent molar volumes are calculated from densities using the relationship,

$$\phi_v = M/d - [1000(d - d^*)/mdm^*]$$

where, m is the molality, d is the density of the solution, d^* is the density of water, and M is the molar mass of the solute.

Description of calorimetric set-up : The experimental set-up for measurement of integral enthalpies of solution is described in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the precision calorimetric set-up.

The isoperibol calorimeter, essentially similar to the submarine calorimeter described by Cobble *et al.* and Subramanian and Ahluwalia⁶⁷, is a double-walled Dewer type flask of about 600 ml

capacity fitted with a 71/60 standard taper joint and an evacuated double-walled stopper. A large water-bath (~60 cm x 60 cm x 60 cm) was used as a constant temperature jacket around the calorimeter. A Tronac PTC-40 (Tronac Inc., U.S.A.), proportional temperature controller coupled with a cooled-heater assembly was employed to control the bath temperature within ± 0.0005 K. The coolant was circulated by a MK-70 ultracryostat which could deliver cold fluid (temperature range 243 - 313 K) with approximately constant flow-rate and temperature stability of ± 0.1 K. The temperature sensing element in the calorimeter was a thermistor obtained from (Yellow Springs, U.S.A.). It had a resistance equal to 10 k Ω at 298.15 K and had a negative temperature coefficient of resistance of about 4% per degree. It was connected to a Wheatstone bridge through copper leads and shielded cable. The thermistor formed one arm of the Wheatstone bridge. The output voltage of the bridge was amplified with a gain of 10^5 with Keithley 140 nanovolt amplifier. An amplified signal was recorded on a Bryans Southern 28000 (Mitchan, U.K.) potentiometric strip-chart recorder. Temperature resolution of the system was 1×10^{-5} K. The resistance of the calibration heater was measured at every temperature to an accuracy of $\pm 0.02\%$. A Keithley 227 constant current source (stability $\pm 0.005\%$) coupled with a digital timer DET-203 (Thermadyne, India) was used for electric calibration.

Operational procedure : Dissolution of the sample was carried out by breaking the sample bulb with a vertical movement of the sample bulb holder to hit the anvil fixed at the bottom of the calorimeter. The heat, q , in joules evolved or absorbed during the dissolution of the sample is calculated from the equation,

$$q = \frac{I^2 R t (\Delta R_s)}{(\Delta R_c)}$$

where, I represents the current in amperes, t is the time in sec of passage of current during the calibration, R is the resistance in ohms of the calibration heater, and ΔR_s and ΔR_c are the changes in the resistance of the thermistor during dissolution and calibration, respectively. The value of q when divided by the number of moles of the sample would give the integral enthalpy of solution per mole, ΔH_s , at that particular concentration. The accuracy obtained was 0.3% (Ref. 68).

Heat capacity of solutions : The Picker micro-flow calorimeter⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ (Fig. 5) is simple in design and operation, and yields directly the ratio of the specific heat capacity of a solution to that of a reference liquid, usually the solvent. The specifications are based on actual measurements done with standard instruments manufactured by Sodev Inc. : sensitivity, 5×10^{-5} JK⁻¹ cm⁻³; precision, $\pm 0.3\%$ up to limit of sensitivity ; reproducibility, $\pm 0.2\%$ under the best condition ; response time, 3 s or less ; optimum flow for measurement, 0.5 ml by min. Under steady-state condition, this measurement is

Fig. 5. Schematic of specific heat calorimeter: (A) reference liquid, (B) measured liquid, (C) exhaust liquid, ($Z_{1,2}$) heating elements, ($T_{1,2}$) thermistors and (V) valve.

independent of the heat capacity of the instrument, the flow-rate, and the induced change in temperature of the liquids. Basically, the instrument acts as a thermal balance. Under similar conditions of heat and liquid flow, any difference in the specific heat capacities of the liquids in twin-flow cells will cause a difference in the final equilibrium temperatures. The liquid entering the flow-cell is thermostatted. Then, under steady-state conditions of liquid flow and power input, a temperature gradient is established.

When liquids with different C_p flow in the cells, the difference in temperature between the reference and working flow cells is sensed by the detectors (thermistors) which form two arms of a bridge (D); the signal arising from the bridge is amplified, and through an appropriate electronic circuit (C), is used to change the power input to the working flow cell. The thermal feedback process will maintain the same temperature gradient in the working flow-cell as in the reference one. Therefore, the instrument essentially measures the change ΔP in power input necessary to maintain the final temperature of the liquid in the working flow-cell equal to that of the reference liquid of known specific heat capacity. Provided that the heat capacity varies only in a linear fashion with temperature in the interval ($T_1 - T_0$), the ratio of the specific heat capacity of a liquid (C_p) to that of a reference liquid (C_p^0) will be given in terms of the ratio of the power inputs to the working and reference flow-cells by the relation,

$$C_p/C_p^0 = (1 + \Delta P/P) (P^0/P)$$

which is valid when the flow rates and temperature rises are the same on each side. The steady flow

of liquids in the calorimeter is achieved with a precision analytical pump, with a flow range of $0-2 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, connected to the working cell (a). At $0.87 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, the stability is better than 0.1%.

Solvent is first sent through both the cells so as to establish the base line. The solution from the second pump is then injected into the working cell at the same flow rate, and the relative specific heat capacity measurements are carried through until the solution reaches the reference flow-cell. Finally, water is pumped back into the calorimeter. For a given flow rate, the time of observation will be determined by the length of tube joining the working and the reference flow-cells. The overall volume of solution required for one measurement is about 4 cm^3 . The overall time required for one measurement is of the order of 5 min (flow rate, $0.87 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$).

It, therefore, eliminates time-consuming numerical calculations and may represent a noteworthy advance in obtaining heat capacities of solutions with sufficient accuracy.

Description of density meter: The schematic diagram for the density meter DMA 60/602 (Anton Paar, Austria) alongwith its temperature controlling system is given in Fig. 6. Density determination is based on the principle of time lapse measurement for a certain number of oscillations of a vibrating U-shaped sample tube which is filled with sample liquid or through which the fluid flows continuously. Resonant frequency of the U-tube is sustained and monitored by appropriate electronic devices. The natural vibration period, t , of the U-tube is related

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram of the digital density-meter DMA 602/60 and the closed loop ultra-thermostat.

to the density of liquid (d) filling the tube, by equation (1) as has been shown by Kratky and coworkers^{7,8,9}.

$$d = A + Bt^2 \quad (1)$$

where, A and B are constants for a given mechanical system of vibrating U-tube. The density difference between two liquids is

$$d = d_1 - d_2 = B(t_1^2 - t_2^2) \quad (2)$$

Provided the number of vibrations for which the time lapse T is measured remains constant, the density difference can also be given as

$$d = d_1 - d_2 = K(T_1^2 - T_2^2)$$

where, T_1 and T_2 are time lapses for n vibrations of oscillator tube corresponding to liquid (1) and (2), respectively, and K is the instrument constant.

DMA 602 density measuring cell: DMA 602 density measuring cell consists of a U-shaped borosilicate oscillator sample tube fused into a double-walled glass cylinder. To ensure the best performance for the instrument, cell temperature stability better than ± 0.01 K is required. A closed-loop circulating ultra-thermostat was constructed for this purpose. It consists of a glass vessel of about 2.5 litre capacity placed in a thermally insulated casing, a Tranac PTC-40 proportional temperature controller, a circulation pump, a heat-exchanger and an MK-70 ultra-cryostat. Temperature range over which the circulating ultra-thermostat could be used was from 298 to 348 K with a stability of ± 0.005 K; flow-rate of the pump being about 50 ml s^{-1} .

DMA 60 electronic processing unit: Analog signal generated in synchronism with the oscillating sample tube in the density measuring cell is transmitted into the electronic processing unit DMA-60. This signal is amplified and displayed digitally.

Operational procedure: Since the differential measurements were performed, it was ensured by completely filling the measuring cell that equal volumes of both the sample and reference liquid were used. Disposable, polyethylene syringes ($\sim 2 \text{ ml}$) were used for this purpose. The instrument, K, was found using air-free pure water and dry air as standards. The reproducibility of the measurements was better than 3 ppm for dilute solutions.

Thermodynamic investigations of aqueous solutions of model compounds:

There are three distinct types of groups, viz. ionic, hydrophobic and polyfunctional hydrophilic, commonly found in biological macromolecules. Because of their complex nature, a direct study of biological processes is a difficult task. The approach generally applied is to dissect the complex process into simpler experimentally amenable ones and derive the relevant informations from the study of smaller model compounds. This type of strategy has been very helpful in understanding some phenomena such as protein denaturation and molecular organisation of cell membrane, particularly fluid mosaic model.

Heat capacity changes and partial molar heat capacities of several amino.acids in water^{7,8,9}:

The effect of size (on the non-polar part) and functional group of a hydrophobic solute on its hydrophobic hydration is of particular interest. It is recognised that the increase in alkyl-chain length of aliphatic and aromatic solutes results in an increase in their ΔC_p° and \bar{C}_p° values, which in turn, is now accepted as an indication of an increase in the hydrophobic-hydration propensity (or increase in water-structure-enhancement propensity) of these solutes.

It is remarkable to note that an increase in the alkyl-chain length results in an uniform increment in ΔC_p° (about $60 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ (about $90 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) per CH_2 group irrespective of the nature of the monofunctional group. Recently, it has also been observed that an increment in the alkyl part of aromatic hydrophobic solutes, results in a much smaller increase in ΔC_p° per CH_2 group. It would be interesting to see how hydrophobic hydration is modified by the presence of two (or more) functional groups, such as those present in amino acids.

The change in the relative position of NH_3^+ and COO^- groups could alter the electrostriction of water which could indirectly also modify the overall hydrophobic hydration propensity of amino acids. Thus, amino acids would seem to form a good model system not only for studying quantitatively the effect of two functional groups on hydrophobic hydration but also the effect of changing the relative positions of the functional groups. In addition, the study of aqueous solutions of various isomers of amino acids could also resolve the contradictions reported in the literature on the effect of branching of alkyl groups of hydrophobic hydration.

With these objectives in mind, the values of the integral enthalpies of solution of amino acids in aqueous solution at infinite dilution, were determined at 25 and 35°, and therefrom, were derived the limiting values of heat capacity changes on dissolution, ΔC_p° , and the partial molar heat capacities $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$. Values of ΔH_s° for α -amino acids and amino acids with the NH_3^+ group at the terminal position at 25° are plotted in Fig. 7 as a function of the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain. A similar trend is observed for the ΔH_s° values at 35°. The values of ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ of α -amino acids are plotted as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain at 30° in Fig. 8. The values of ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ of amino acids having the NH_3^+ group at the terminal position and are plotted as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain at 30° in Fig. 9. The effect, on ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$, of shifting the position of the NH_3^+ group away from the COO^- group in some amino acids is summarised in Fig. 10.

The ΔH_s° of α -amino acids and amino acids with terminal NH_3^+ groups, shown in Fig. 7, indicate a definite minima at position C_4 . Such minima have also been observed for other homologous series of compounds. Since ΔH_s° is affected by a number of effects, no attempt has been made to interpret these results in structural terms. The heat capacity for a homologous series of α -amino acids (aminoacetic acid (glycine), DL-2-aminovaleric acid (DL-norleucine)), given in Fig. 8, show that each CH_2 group results in a uniform increment of about 60 and 67 $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in ΔC_p° at 25 and 30°, respectively, and of about 88 and 93 $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ value at 25 and 30°, respectively.

Fig. 7. Integral enthalpy of solution of amino acids in water at infinite dilution at 25° as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain: (●) amino acids (the value of DL-norleucine for $n=5$ has a much larger uncertainty) and (○) amino acids with NH_3^+ at the terminal position.

Fig. 8. Heat capacity change on dissolution, ΔC_p° , and partial molar heat capacity $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$, of α -amino acids at 30° as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain.

It is interesting to note that the increment in $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ (and ΔC_p°) per CH_2 group in α -amino acids is the same as has been found earlier in homologous series of monofunctional compounds, such as the aliphatic carboxylic acids and their sodium salts, ethers, amines and alcohols. Since an increase in the value of ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ is associated with an increase in the hydrophobic-hydration effect, the uniform increase in ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p_2}^\circ$ value for the CH_2 group increment indicates that the hydrophobic

hydration or structure-enhancing propensity of α -amino acids increases with alkyl-chain length and that the electrostriction effect (structure-breaking effect) due to dipolar character remains constant and independent of the alkyl-chain length. However, for homologous series of amino acids where the NH_3^+ group is at the terminal position, the results indicate (Fig. 9) that the increase in ΔC_p^0 and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ per CH_2 group is not uniform but rather varies as one goes from glycine to β -alanine, γ -aminobutyric

Fig. 9. Heat-capacity change on dissolution and partial molar heat capacity of amino acids having an NH_3^+ group at the terminal position, at 30° , as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain.

acid, δ -aminovaleric acid and ϵ -aminocaproic acid. From the data, as illustrated in Fig. 10, it can be observed that the shift of NH_3^+ group from the α -position to the β -position reduces the value of ΔC_p^0 and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ by about $57 \pm 5 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. However, the shift of a NH_3^+ group from the β - to the γ -position results in a lower reduction (about $28 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), but nonetheless it is still significant. The effect continues upto at least the ϵ -position, where the overall decrease in ΔC_p^0 turns out to be about $122 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The results for isomers of amino acids, namely α -aminobutyric acid and α -aminoisobutyric acid, β -aminobutyric acid and β -aminoisobutyric acid, DL-valine and DL-norvaline, L-leucine, and DL-norleucine indicate that branching of alkyl groups does not affect the partial molar heat capacity and hence the hydrophobic-hydration propensity of amino acids. The substitution of H by OH group results in a decrease of about $26 \pm 8 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in ΔC_p^0 and of about $21 \pm 4 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$. Spink and Wadso have also observed a decrease of about $20 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ for α -alanine and serine at 25° . Substitution of CH_3 by the $\text{CH}_2\text{CO.NH}_2$ group results in a decrease of about $27 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$

Fig. 10. Change in partial molar heat capacity as a function of shift of the NH_3^+ with respect to the COO^- group from α to β , γ , δ and ϵ .

in ΔC_p^0 and of about $11 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$. Comparison of results of DL-alanine and L-phenylalanine indicates that the addition of a phenyl group results in an increase in ΔC_p^0 and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ by about 157 and $239 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. This is in good agreement with the results of Spink and Wadso. It is also interesting to note that addition of CH_2 to L-asparagine, which contains the CO.NH_2 group in addition to NH_3^+ and COO^- groups, results in about the same increase in ΔC_p^0 ($64 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ ($88 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) as found for other amino acids.

Enthalpies, heat capacities and apparent molar volumes of transfer of some amino acids from water to aqueous t-butanol¹⁶ :

The TBA—water system, which is the most extensively studied among the various aqueous alcohol solvent systems, was chosen because maximum pronounced effects, *viz.* the appearance of extreme in the equilibrium properties of the solute molecules, are observed as the co-solvent composition is changed. Furthermore, because of the zwitterionic nature of amino acids, it would be interesting to see how their behaviour contrasts with those of electrolytes and non-polar groups in the TBA-water system. Such a comparison should also lead to a better understanding of the interaction of electrolytes and non-polar compounds not only with water but also with each other.

The amino acids chosen are glycine (GLY), for aqueous solution properties typical of electrolytes (*i.e.* structure-breakers, which decrease the hydrogen-bonded structure of water), α -alanine (α -ALA), α -amino-n-butyric acid (α -ABA) and L-valine

(L-VAL), for properties typical of hydrophobic solutes (structure-makers, which enhance the hydrogen-bonded structure of water). β -Alanine (β -ALA) and δ -amino-n-valeric acid (δ -VAL) were selected to investigate the effect of the position of the amino group in the sidechain of amino acids on the transfer functions.

Integral enthalpies of solution (ΔH_s) of the amino acids were measured at 298.15 and 308.15 K in TBA-water mixtures at various TBA mole fractions (0.02–0.15). The final concentration of amino acid in the solution was very low, always 2×10^{-3} mol kg⁻¹. The ΔH_{tr} against x_{TBA} profile (Fig. 11) shows that the value of ΔH_{tr} increases with increasing TBA concentration, giving rise to a maximum at ca. 0.1 mole fraction of TBA for all the amino

Fig. 11. Enthalpy of transfer of various amino acids from water to aqueous t-butanol at 298 K: (Δ) GLY, (\bullet) β -ALA, (\square) α -ALA, (\blacktriangle) ABA and (\circ) L-VAL.

acids. An increase in the maximum value of ΔH_{tr} is also observed as the length of the alkyl side-chain increases. This is in agreement with the earlier observations that the higher the hydrophobicity of the solute, higher is the endothermic maximum in the ΔH_{tr} against x_{TBA} curve.

Heat capacities of transfer $\Delta C_{p,tr}$ of amino acids from water to TBA-water mixtures at 303.15 K, are shown in Fig. 12 as a function of TBA mole fraction. The results indicate a sharp decrease in $\Delta C_{p,tr}$ with the increasing concentration of TBA reaching a minimum at ca. 0.1 mole fraction of TBA and after that increasing slightly. In addition, a discontinuity in the slope is observed at ca. 0.04 mole fraction of TBA. This discontinuity becomes more prominent with increasing size of alkyl side-chain of the amino acids, and in fact a small maximum is observed in the case of L-valine.

Fig. 12. Heat capacity of transfer of some amino acids from water to aqueous t-butanol at 303 K; symbols as Fig. 1; error bar shows experimental error.

The apparent molar volume of transfer at 0.1 mol kg⁻¹ solute concentration of GLY, α -ALA, β -ALA, α -ABA, L-VAL and δ -VAL against TBA mole fraction are given in Fig. 13. Fairly sharp changes are observed in the region where ϕ_v of TBA goes through a minimum $\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$ of amino acids, except GLY, show a minimum around 0.03 mole

Fig. 13. Volumes of transfer of some amino acids from water to aqueous t-butanol at 298 K; symbols as Fig. 1.

fraction of TBA. Minimum value of $\Delta\phi_{tr}$ decreases from $-0.26 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for β -ALA to $-1.71 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for L-VAL; the order found to be L-VAL < δ -VAL < α -ABA < α -ALA < β -ALA.

The thermodynamic transfer functions of these amino acids are not a result of changes in the acid or base dissociation constants of the zwitterionic amino acids in the mixed solvent. This is evident from the fact that the dissociation constants of amino acids are very small and change little in aqueous alcohol mixtures.

The transfer functions may be interpreted in terms of water structure-making or -breaking effects of the solutes, as has been postulated by Frank and Evans. This approach has been successful in the case of transfer of amino acids from water to aqueous urea solutions. Up to 0.04 mole fraction of TBA is believed to enhance the structure of water. Thus, according to this approach the signs and magnitudes of the transfer functions may be explained by considering transfer of the solutes as going from a structured medium, water, to a relatively more structured medium, TBA-water. However, Avedikian and coworkers and Desnoyers and coworkers have indicated that such a simple approach fails to explain the observed trends in the transfer functions of a variety of solutes on going from water to aqueous mixtures containing hydrophobic co-solvents. In the present case also, the values of ΔH_{tr} of all the amino acids are positive, while opposite signs would have been predicted from this approach for a water structure-breaker (GLY or β -ALA) and a water structure-maker (α -ABA or L-VAL). In ternary aqueous systems containing TBA (or any other hydrophobic co-solvent) several effects other than water structure modification by solute or co-solvent are interacting; these should be considered in developing a plausible explanation of the observed transfer functions. A better approach would be one that also involves the solute-solute interactions.

Kozak *et al.* have produced a theory based on the McMillan-Mayer theory of solutions that permits the formal separation of the effects due to interactions between pairs of solute molecules and those due to interactions involving three or more solute molecules. This approach has been further discussed by Friedman and Krishnan and Franks *et al.* in order to include solute-solvent interactions, at least involving indirectly the solvent-solvent interactions in the solvation spheres. Following the treatment of Friedman and Krishnan, the thermodynamic transfer functions, $\Delta Y_{tr}(W \rightarrow W + TBA)$, can be expressed in terms of interactions involving the solute and co-solvent molecules. As the solute concentrations are very small, *i.e.* $m_A \ll m_B$ (A stands for an amino acid and B for TBA), solute interactions involving the molecules of species A only can be ignored and the transfer function may be written as

$$\Delta Y_{tr}(W \rightarrow W + TBA) = 2y_{AB}m_B + 3y_{ABB}m_B^2 + 4y_{ABBB}m_B^3 + \dots \quad (3)$$

where, y_{AB} , y_{ABB} , *etc.*, are, respectively, the pair, triplet, *etc.*, interaction coefficients corresponding to a particular thermodynamic property (*i.e.* if $Y=H$, $y_{AB}=h_{AB}$, *etc.*). This treatment requires the concentrations to be expressed relative to pure solvent, *i.e.* m_B is the number of moles of TBA per kg of pure water. The interaction coefficients corresponding to enthalpy, heat capacity and apparent molar volume of transfer of various amino acids are listed in Table 1.

The thermodynamic transfer functions of solutes give a measure of the perturbation of the solvent and co-solvent molecules in the vicinity of a solute molecule, along with the changes in solute properties. We therefore discuss briefly the solute interactions in the binary system water-TBA and compare them with the interactions in a ternary system. Various interaction coefficients in water-TBA solutions

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC INTERACTION COEFFICIENTS OF SOME AMINO ACIDS IN AQUEOUS t-BUTANOL SOLUTIONS

	298 K			308 K		
	h_{AB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻¹	h_{ABB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻²	h_{ABBB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻³	h_{AB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻¹	h_{ABB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻²	h_{ABBB} J mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻³
GLY	692	116	-21	528	133	-23
β -ALA	708	133	-26	685	65	-17
α -ALA	840	121	-23	789	125	-27
α -ABA	976	104	-19	1033	59	-18
L-VAL	679	289	-44	813	261	-48

	303 K			298 K		
	c_{AB} J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻¹	c_{ABB} J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻²	c_{ABBB} J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻³	v_{AB} cm ³ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻¹	v_{ABB} cm ³ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻²	v_{ABBB} cm ³ mol ⁻¹ (mol kg ⁻¹) ⁻³
GLY	-13	0.4	0.01	-0.18	0.18	-0.11
β -ALA	-12	-2.3	0.19	-0.54	0.22	-0.013
α -ALA	5	-4.3	0.26	-0.77	0.28	-0.017
α -ABA	9	-6.1	0.37	-1.01	0.29	-0.016
δ -VAL	—	—	—	-1.18	0.30	-0.016
L-VAL	28	-9.5	0.48	-1.36	0.35	-0.020

obtained from the relative partial molar thermodynamic properties *via* equation (4) are available in the literature.

$$\bar{V}_B - \bar{V}_B^0 = \nu_{BB} m_B + \nu_{BBB} m_B^2 + \nu_{BBBB} m_B^3 + \dots \quad (4)$$

Interaction coefficients corresponding with apparent molar volume have also been calculated from this work.

The enthalpic interaction coefficients in water-TBA binary mixtures, h_{BB} and h_{BBB} , are positive, $656 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ and $334 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-2}$, respectively. Any interaction among the solute molecules occurs through the overlap of 'hydration co-spheres'. The overlap of co-spheres squeezes out some water molecules from the hydrophobic hydration sphere of TBA to the bulk which results in a net decrease in the hydrogen-bonded structure of water, thus ΔH (interaction) > 0 . The negative slope in the ϕ_v against x_{TBA} curve, has also been attributed to a reduction in the hydrophobic hydration 'per mole of solute' through an overlap of the co-spheres.

Progressive destructurement of the hydration spheres due to overlap of co-spheres would cause the ϕ_{C_p} to decrease as the TBA concentration is increased, giving rise to a negative value of c_{BB} . On the contrary, ϕ_{C_p} has a positive slope up to 0.04 mole fraction of TBA [$c_{BB} = 7.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$].

Recently, Clark *et al.* have carried out a statistical mechanical study of dilute aqueous solutions of alcohols (including TBA). From their findings for the entropy of interaction of solute molecules they suggest that it is necessary to consider the thermodynamic state of squeezed-out water and that of the water involved in the hydration co-spheres and its overlap. They conclude that the overlap of two hydrophobic hydration co-spheres squeezes some water molecules out to the bulk but the resulting hydration spheres of the solvent-separated solute pairs are subject to a greater constraint than were the individual shells. If this constraint further immobilises the water molecules in the shared solvation shells it could lead to a small positive value of c_{BB} .

In fact, in a molecular dynamics study of an aqueous solution of neon, Geiger *et al.* have found that two water molecules remain fixed for rather longer times in the plane between two neon atoms. The decreased mobility of water molecules in the solvation sphere of hydrophobic molecules is further evidenced by nuclear magnetic relaxation data of some hydrophobic solutes.

At concentrations > 0.04 mole fraction, cooperative association processes similar to that of micelle formation give rise to the increasing ϕ_v for TBA, and decreasing ϕ_{C_p} . At still higher concentration ($x_{\text{TBA}} > 0.1$), insufficient water is probably available for the formation of long-range ordered networks and the hydrophobic effect is dominated by hydrogen bonding and dipolar effects. Consequently, the clusters of TBA molecules break down. The

mixing process resembles to that of two normal liquids and ϕ_v and ϕ_{C_p} tend to attain molar values of pure TBA.

With this background to the interaction in TBA-water mixtures, it seems possible to explain the thermodynamic transfer functions observed for the ternary system in terms of the overlap of hydration co-spheres of the solutes and that of TBA. The positive values of all the pair and triplet interaction coefficients h_{AB} and h_{ABB} signify a net decrease in the hydrogen-bonded structure of water due to the overlap of co-spheres of amino acids and TBA. In the case of glycine and β -alanine, the charged head-groups COO^- and NH_3^+ dominate the interactions. The hydration spheres of GLY and β -ALA are mainly composed of charge-dipole forces. Therefore, an overlap of the co-spheres of GLY or β -ALA with that of TBA would squeeze out water molecules mainly from the hydrophobic hydration sphere of TBA. On the other hand, in the higher homologues, apart from the hydrophilic hydration of the charged zwitterionic head-group, there exists a hydrophobic hydration co-sphere for the alkyl side-chain. In the case of overlap of TBA co-spheres with that of higher amino acids, therefore, some water molecules should be released from the co-sphere of the side-chains also, giving rise to larger h_{AB} values for the higher homologues than for GLY or β -ALA.

The differences in h_{AB} for (glycine- α -alanine) and (α -alanine- α -aminobutyric acid) give a value of *ca.* $142 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ at 298 K and *ca.* $253 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ at 308 K for the (CH_2 -TBA) enthalpy pair-interaction coefficient, $h_{(\text{CH}_2, \text{-TBA})}$. The higher value of $h_{(\text{CH}_2, \text{-TBA})}$ at 308 K compared with that at 298 K implies that the pair-interaction coefficients for heat capacities, c_{AB} , should increase with increasing size of the amino acids; this is observed. The coefficient $h_{(\text{CH}_2, \text{-TBA})}$ at 298 K can be compared with the same value in the literature. The value of $h_{(\text{CH}_2, \text{-TBA})}$ is $585 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ from the data given by Friedman and Krishnan for h_{XY} of several alcohols; where, ethanol, n-propanol and n-butanol were taken as solute X and TBA as solute Y. Franks *et al.* have raised doubts about the reliability of the values of Friedman and Krishnan and given the various enthalpy pair and triplet interaction coefficients for a series of alcohols which agree well with those observed by Kenttamaa and Cassel and Wood. From the data of Franks *et al.* a value of $268 \text{ J mol}^{-1}(\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ is found for $h_{(\text{CH}_2, \text{-TBA})}$, which is significantly higher than our value. One reason for the apparent discrepancy could be the different chemical environments around the methene groups in alcohols and amino acids.

The smaller values of h_{AB} for L-valine at both 298 and 308 K, suggest the existence of some orientation-dependent contribution to the pairwise hydrophobic interaction. Valine has a branched isopropyl side-chain, unlike the unbranched side-chains of the other amino acids studied. The branching of the alkyl side-chain probably imposes

restrictions on the pair interactions, thus the h_{AB} values of valine are smaller.

The ratio h_{ABB}/h_{AB} is treated as a measure of the cooperativity of the hydrophobic association. For GLY, α -ALA and α -ABA, the ratio h_{ABB}/h_{AB} ranges from 0.1 to 0.25; on the other hand, for valine this ratio is 0.4, implying a higher tendency of cooperative interaction in the water-TBA-valine system.

For glycine and β -alanine c_{AB} values are negative. An extensive collapse of the hydrophobic hydration co-sphere of TBA due to charged portions of glycine and β -alanine should result in a negative heat capacity pair-interaction coefficient. The positive sign of c_{AB} for the higher homologues indicates that the alkyl side-chains of these molecules are behaving like another TBA molecule (*vide supra*), and the hydrophobic effect of the alkyl side-chain overcomes the electrostatic effects of the zwitterionic head-group. In this way c_{AB} increases with increasing side-chain length of the amino acid. Similarly, the sign and magnitude of v_{AB} is negative, indicating a reduction in volume as the association commences. This is consistent with what is happening in the binary system TBA-water. The magnitude of v_{AB} increases with increasing size of the amino acids. The same has been observed for the pair interaction involving hydrophobic solute molecules in the binary system. For instance v_{xx} of alcohols in aqueous solutions are in the order: methanol (-0.14) < ethanol (-0.15) < n-propanol (-0.71) < n-butanol (-1.7) < t-butanol (-2.3 ; -2.33 , this work), in units of $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} (\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$.

Negative values of the triplet terms c_{ABB} and a positive sign for v_{ABB} come from the collapse of the co-spheres due to aggregation of amino-acid side-chains with that of TBA in such a way that the alkyl groups are removed from effective contact with water, a process similar to micelle formation. For glycine c_{ABB} is very small, nearly zero; accordingly there is no abrupt change in the $\Delta C_{p,ir}$ against x_{TBA} curve; this suggests the absence of cooperative aggregation in the GLY-TBA-water system. On the other hand, the increasing magnitudes of c_{ABB} and v_{ABB} of higher homologues indicate that the tendency for cooperative aggregation increases with increasing length of the amino-acid side-chains.

The higher-order terms h_{ABBB} , c_{ABBB} , and v_{ABBB} are very small. Their signs correspond to a levelling-off of the ΔH_{ir} against x_{TBA} , $\Delta C_{p,ir}$ against x_{TBA} and $\Delta \phi_{v,ir}$ against x_{TBA} curves, respectively, after ca. 0.1 mole fraction of TBA. The dominating contributions of hydrogen bonding and dipolar interactions over those of the hydrophobic effects in highly concentrated TBA solutions can probably explain the signs of these higher-order interaction coefficients. Exothermic effects would be expected for hydrogen bonding or mutually attractive dipolar interactions. Similarly, inter-molecular hydrogen bonding is accompanied by a decrease in volume and increase in heat capacities. Thus at high TBA

concentrations, hydrogen bonding between the charged zwitterionic portion of the amino acid and the hydroxyl group of TBA should give a negative h_{ABBB} , positive c_{ABBB} and negative v_{ABBB} ; however, these should probably be of same magnitude, irrespective of the size of the amino acid. In the case of enthalpy and volume of transfer, we indeed observe approximately equal values for h_{ABBB} and v_{ABBB} for all amino acids (except valine), the average being $-21 \pm 4 \text{ J mol}^{-1} (\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$ and $-0.016 \pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} (\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$, respectively. However, with the heat capacities of transfer the c_{ABBB} values are scattered from 0.01 to $0.48 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} (\text{mol kg}^{-1})^{-1}$. Nevertheless, in view of the larger errors in the heat capacity data one can assume the c_{ABBB} values as nearly the same for the various amino acids.

In conclusion, the thermodynamic transfer functions of amino acids from water to TBA-water mixtures reflect the combined effects of various hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions in these solutions. Signs and magnitudes of pair and higher-order interaction coefficients corresponding to the thermodynamic transfer functions suggest that hydrophobic association of amino acid and TBA molecules through pair interactions are important up to ca. 0.04 mole fraction of TBA while cooperative aggregation is favoured at higher concentrations (up to 0.1 mole fraction of TBA). Extensive collapse of the long-range order of water structure does not permit any hydrophobic effects to dominate at TBA concentrations >0.1 mole fraction. The zwitterionic portion of the amino acids partially breaks down the hydrogen-bonded network of water molecules in the solvation sphere of TBA at lower TBA concentrations. At high TBA concentrations the hydrogen bonding or dipolar interactions between the zwitterions and hydroxyl groups of TBA is probably a dominating factor.

Alcohol induced conformational transitions of proteins and polypeptides⁷⁷

Alcohols are known to produce a denaturing effect on the native conformation of proteins. The widely accepted viewpoint at the present time is that alcohols denature the native conformation of the proteins by 'dissolving out' the hydrocarbon interior of the macromolecule by a hydrophobic bonding mechanisms, the denaturation being increased with the increasing alkyl residue content. There are, however, anomalies which are difficult to explain by considering only the hydrophobic effects. For instance, coil-helix transitions of poly-L-ornithine and poly-L-glutamic acid in the presence of a variety of alcohols studied by Conio *et al.* indicate that increasing alcohol concentration favours the formation of helix and larger the alkyl group of alcohol, the more effective it becomes at stabilising the helical conformation. Conio *et al.* suggest that the crucial factor involved in the stabilisation of helical conformation arises from a decrease in the entropy of mixing of the peptide group with the solvent as the alcohol concentration is increased. A better

knowledge of various interactions of the constituent groups of proteins and polypeptides with the solvent (water) and co-solute (alcohol) may help further in understanding the conformational stability of proteins and polypeptides in presence of the added co-solute. Thermodynamic properties of aqueous solutions of small model compounds containing the constituent groups of proteins and polypeptides are known to provide such information. Accordingly, as a continuation of our earlier attempt, we report the enthalpies and entropies of transfer of the peptide group (CONH) and the peptide backbone unit (CH_2CONH) from water to aqueous alcohol solutions. These transfer functions are derived from the data on model compounds, *viz.* diglycine, glycine, α -alanine, and β -alanine.

$T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of glycine, α -alanine, β -alanine, and diglycine have been calculated by combining the ΔH_{tr} data with the ΔG_{tr} values computed from solubility data. Since the solubilities of the amino acids and diglycine in TBA-water mixtures were not available in the literature, ΔG_{tr} (and $T\Delta S_{tr}$) were evaluated only for ethanol-water mixtures. The following relation given by Nozaki and Tanford was employed to obtain the ΔG_{tr} values corrected for solute-solute self-interaction,

$$\Delta G_{tr} = RT \ln(N_w/N_a) + RT \ln(\gamma_w/\gamma_a) \quad (1)$$

where, N_w and N_a are the solubilities in terms of mole fraction in pure water and in ethanol-water mixture, respectively, and γ_w and γ_a are the activity coefficients of solute at saturation in water and ethanol-water mixture. Correction for the solute-solute self-interaction in the ΔG_{tr} values is included in the last term, $RT \ln(\gamma_w/\gamma_a)$, with the activity coefficients required for such corrections were taken from Hutchens. The correction terms applied for β -alanine were those for α -alanine were not available (*vide infra*).

The $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of glycine, α -alanine, β -alanine and diglycine calculated as above are plotted in Fig. 15 as a function of the alcohol mole fraction. Difference of the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of glycine and diglycine from the smoothed curve of Fig. 15 gave the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ contribution of the CH_2CONH group and that of diglycine and β -alanine gave the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values are also included in Fig. 15. $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of the CONH group remains negative at all concentrations of ethanol, in contrast to the positive $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of the amino acids, diglycine, or CH_2CONH moiety upto 0.1-0.12 mole fractions of alcohol. $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of the CONH group are also evaluated from the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ curves of α -alanine and diglycine (Fig. 15). Even in this case, the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values for the CONH group always remain negative. Nevertheless, the transfer entropies of the CONH group obtained from the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ curves of glycine and β -alanine should be more realistic because both diglycine and β -alanine contain terminal $-\text{NH}_3^+$ and $-\text{COO}^-$ charged moieties.

There is a sharp increase in the enthalpies of transfer of diglycine and the amino acids

from water to TBA-water and ethanol-water mixtures (Fig. 14). The changes in acid or base dissociation constants of amphiprotic zwitterion-diglycine in the aqueous alcohol mixtures are very little and thus cannot be responsible for the observed trends in the ΔH_{tr} . The interpretation similar to that advanced for the ΔH_{tr} of amino acids by Mishra and Ahluwalia^{7b} can explain the behaviour of transfer enthalpies of diglycine also.

Fig. 14. Enthalpies of transfer of glycine, β -alanine, and diglycine from water to aqueous alcohol mixtures at 298.15 K: () glycine/*tert.*-butyl alcohol-water, (○) glycine/ethanol-water, (Δ) β -alanine/*tert.*-butyl alcohol-water, (●) β -alanine/ethanol-water, (▼) diglycine/*tert.*-butyl alcohol-water and (Δ) diglycine/ethanol-water.

Mishra and Ahluwalia^{7b} rationalised the sign and magnitude of the thermodynamic transfer functions of amino acids from water to TBA-water mixtures in terms of destructive overlap of hydration co-spheres of the solute molecules. Properties of the water molecules in the hydration co-sphere depend on the nature of solute species. The overlap of the co-sphere of a hydrophobic solute (alcohol) with that of any other solute molecule (alcohol or amino acid or diglycine) results in a net removal of some water molecules of the 'structured' region to comparatively less structured region with a concomitant gain in entropy ($\Delta S > 0$) and enthalpy ($\Delta H > 0$) due to decrease in the degree of hydrogen bondedness (Fig. 16). Hence, the ΔH_{tr} and $T\Delta S_{tr}$ values are positive (Figs. 14 and 15).

For glycine, β -alanine and diglycine the ΔH_{tr} values from water to TBA-water are higher than those from water to ethanol-water. This difference may be due to the difference in water structure promoting capability of TBA and ethanol. The hydrophobic hydration co-sphere of TBA would be larger than that of ethanol in aqueous solutions. Therefore, the interaction of glycine, β -alanine or diglycine molecules would produce a disruption of

Fig. 15. Entropies of transfer from water to aqueous ethanol mixtures at 298.15 K: (○) glycine, (▲) α-alanine, (○) β-alanine, (□) diglycine, (×) CH₂CONH, (◇) CONH (from diglycine and β-alanine) and (---) CONH (from diglycine and α-alanine).

the hydrogen bonded structure in the co-spheres of TBA to a greater extent than that of ethanol in aqueous solutions.

$T\Delta S_{tr}$ values of the solutes increase with the increase in the ethanol concentration, showing a maximum around 0.1 mole fraction followed by a decrease with further increase in alcohol concentration (Fig. 15). The levelling-off of the ΔH_{tr} vs alcohol mole fraction curves (Fig. 15) and decreasing values of $T\Delta S_{tr}$ after 0.1 mole fraction of alcohol (Fig. 15) can be interpreted as arising from the dominating effects of hydrogen bonding and dipolar interactions between alcohol and charged

and dipolar portions of the amino acids and diglycine. A greater number of hydrophilic binding sites available in diglycine molecule compared to that in glycine explains the much sharper decrease in $T\Delta S_{tr}$ of diglycine than that of glycine.

Entropies of transfer of a peptide backbone unit from water to ethanol water mixtures also show typical maximum at 0.1 mole fraction of ethanol. At ethanol concentrations higher than 0.12 mole fraction, $T\Delta S_{tr}$ of CH₂CONH group becomes negative. But the decrease is not as sharp as in the $T\Delta S_{tr}$ of glycine or diglycine. This is probably due to the larger ordering effects produced by charged portions of glycine and diglycine than that by the CONH group of the peptide backbone unit. $T\Delta S_{tr}$ of the CONH group decreases as the concentration of ethanol is increased. Thus the maximum observed in $T\Delta S_{tr}$ of CH₂CONH group results probably from the contribution of the CH₂ group present in the former.

Alcohol induced conformational transitions of proteins and polypeptides :

Brandts and Hunt, Phol, and Asakura *et al.* have observed that low concentrations (8-15%, w/w) of alcohol stabilise the native conformation of protein against denaturation. With the increase in alcohol concentration denaturation of proteins ensues. Observations of Mishra and Ahluwalia⁷⁰ support the views of Eagland that at low alcohol concentrations the hydrophobic hydration cages of apolar side chains are strengthened, thereby making the native conformation of the protein more stable against thermal denaturation. Eagland has also suggested that at alcohol concentrations ≈ 0.04 mole fraction a breakdown in the structure of water causes the protein conformation to collapse. In this connection Mishra and Ahluwalia⁷⁰ have found that there is a marked tendency of cooperative aggregation among the hydrophobic side chains of amino acids and those of alcohols which starts at alcohol mole fraction ≈ 0.04 . Avedikian *et al.*, de Visser *et al.* and Franks *et al.* have also observed a similar type of aggregation of apolar groups of alcohol molecules in aqueous solutions at alcohol concentrations of 0.04–0.1 mole fraction. Such an observation supports the views of Tanford that the denaturation of proteins by alcohols is caused by 'dissolving out' the side chains from the interior of the protein due to so-called 'hydrophobic interaction' among the apolar groups of protein and those of alcohol molecules. However, only the hydrophobic effects can not explain the enhancement in the α-helical conformation of polypeptides observed by Hermans, Conio *et al.*, Chaudhuri and Tsi Yang and Epand and Scheraga and the increasing helix content of proteins observed by Webber and Tanford, Singer, Jirgensons, Inoue and Timasheff, and Hermans *et al.* Increase in the α-helix content comes after gradual addition of alcohols and for globular proteins the increase in α-helix follows the denaturation of native conformation. Conio *et al.* suggest that the helical conformation is stabilised

Fig. 16. Solute-solute interaction through the overlap of hydration co-spheres and resulting changes in the thermodynamic properties.

due to a decrease in the entropy of mixing of the peptide group with the solvent, which, in their opinion, results from an increasing degree of solvent structuring as the alcohol concentration is increased. Nevertheless, the helical conformation is still the most stable at higher alcohol concentrations where the hydrophobic effects are no longer operating (*i.e.* at $X_2 > 0.1$) and the structure of water is almost completely disrupted.

The present observations on the $T \Delta S_{tr}$ of CONH group (Fig. 15) do indicate that the entropy of interaction of CONH group and ethanol in aqueous solution is negative. Entropy of interaction of the CONH group with the alcohol moiety CHOH has been found to be negative by Okamoto *et al.* also. Whether this is a result of the interactions mediated through the typical structure of water or it is due to specific interactions between CONH group and alcohol molecules is open to question. However, the negative sign of $T \Delta S_{tr}$ of the CONH group (and also of the CH_2CONH group) at ethanol concentrations higher than 0.12 mole fractions (Fig. 15) suggests that the hydrogen bonding or dipolar interaction between ethanol and CONH groups leads to a greater decrease in entropy than due to a similar interaction between CONH and water molecules. Thus the negative entropy of mixing of CONH group with aqueous ethanol may be responsible for the enhanced stability of α -helical conformations of proteins and polypeptides at alcohol concentrations higher than *ca.* 0.1 mole fraction.

Apparent molar volumes of some amino acids and peptides in aqueous urea solutions^{7,8,9} :

Details of the nature and mechanism of the interactions in an amino acid (or peptide) - urea - water system have drawn much attention in recent years due to the pronounced ability of urea toward protein denaturation. Despite the numerous reports about urea solutions, the mechanism of the urea denaturation of proteins has not been defined unequivocally. The complicated nature of the action of urea on protein conformations is also reflected in the volume changes associated with the denaturation of proteins (ΔV_{denat}). After considering the inter-atomic distances of several proteins, Klapper suggested that the interior of the protein molecule densely packed and predicted a positive ΔV_{denat} . However, positive, negligible, and negative ΔV_{denat} have been reported to accompany the urea denaturation of proteins. It is known that several factors, such as void volumes, electrostriction of the solvent by the charged moieties, hydrophobic and hydrophilic hydration, together with the van der Waals volume of the peptide chain, contribute to the total volume of the protein and hence to the ΔV_{denat} . Knowledge of the individual contributions of the protein constituent groups to volume changes in aqueous urea solutions may be helpful in understanding how urea affects the interactions of the protein constituent groups with the solvent (water) molecules. In addition, these data may be useful

in rationalising the ΔV_{denat} values. Therefore, continuing our thermodynamic studies on amino acid (or peptide) - urea - water systems, we determined the apparent molar volumes of some acids and peptides in aqueous urea solutions from the density measurements. \bar{V}_a^0 , the apparent molar volumes at infinite dilution of the solutes in 3 and 6 M aqueous urea solutions, evaluated from the extrapolation of ϕ_v by the least-squares method. Changes in \bar{V}^0 , due to transfer of the amino acids and peptides from water to 3 and 6 M aqueous urea solutions (\bar{V}_{tr}^0) were computed from \bar{V}_a^0 in the mixed solvents and in pure water.

The \bar{V}_{tr}^0 values of amino acids and peptides from water to 3 and 6 M aqueous urea solutions are plotted in Fig. 17 against the number of carbon

Fig. 17. Infinite dilution apparent molar volume of transfer of several α -amino acids and peptides from water to aqueous urea solutions at 298.15 K : (O) \bar{V}_{tr}^0 , α -amino acids, water \rightarrow 3 M urea, (□) \bar{V}_{tr}^0 , α -amino acids, water \rightarrow 6 M urea, (●) \bar{V}_{tr}^0 , peptides, water \rightarrow 3 M urea, (Δ) \bar{V}_{tr}^0 , peptides, water \rightarrow 6 M urea. Error bars, maximum probable error.

atoms in the alkyl side chain. Table 2 presents the \bar{V}_{tr}^0 values of the glycyl group (CH_2CONH) and the alkyl side chains derived from the \bar{V}_{tr}^0 values of the peptides and the amino acids. \bar{V}_{tr}^0 of the CH_2CONH group turns out to be $0.8 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The \bar{V}_{tr}^0 value of the alkyl side chains, obtained from the \bar{V}_{tr}^0 data for amino acids, are negative, whereas those obtained from the \bar{V}_{tr}^0 values of the peptides are positive. This startling behaviour is also reflected in the negative and positive slopes of \bar{V}_{tr}^0 vs the number of carbon atom curves (Fig. 17) for amino acids and peptides, respectively.

TABLE 2—INFINITE-DILUTION APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME OF TRANSFER OF GLYCYL GROUP AND ALKYL SIDE CHAINS FROM WATER TO 6 M AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTIONS AT 298.15 K

Group	\bar{V}_{tr}° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	
	From amino acids ^a	From peptides ^b
-CH ₂ COONH-	0.81 ± 0.07 ^c	0.75 ± 0.09 ^d
-OH ₂	-0.18 ± 0.05	-0.06 ± 0.07
-CH ₂ OH ₂	-0.43 ± 0.06	0.25 ± 0.10
-OH ₂ -OH ₂ OH ₂	-0.52 ± 0.12	—
-OH(OH ₂) ₂	—	0.78 ± 0.07
-OH ₂ -OH(OH ₂) ₂	-0.56 ± 0.34	0.78 ± 0.11

^a \bar{V}_{tr}° values of the alkyl side chains are derived from \bar{V}_{tr}° (higher amino acid) - \bar{V}_{tr}° (glycine).
^b \bar{V}_{tr}° values of the alkyl side chains are derived from \bar{V}_{tr}° (higher peptide) - \bar{V}_{tr}° (diglycine).
^c \bar{V}_{tr}° (diglycine) - \bar{V}_{tr}° (glycine).
^d \bar{V}_{tr}° (triglycine) - \bar{V}_{tr}° (diglycine).

Concentration dependence of the thermodynamic properties in aqueous solutions have been explained in terms of the solute-solute interactions. The usual interpretation is that the solute species interact through the overlap of their hydration spheres. In the co-sphere model (Fig. 16), it is usually assumed that the effect of the overlap of two co-spheres is destructive, *i.e.* some water molecules are relaxed to the bulk from one or both the co-spheres. The sign and magnitude of \bar{V}_{tr}° for amino acids and peptides can be rationalised in terms of the overlap of the co-spheres of urea and amino acids (or peptides). Overlap of the co-spheres of amino acids or peptides with those of the same species could be ruled out in discussing the \bar{V}_{tr}° data, since the latter are derived at infinite dilution of the solutes.

Urea may be assumed to have a co-sphere containing fewer water-water hydrogen bonds than bulk water, since urea supposedly destabilises the water structure. For amino acids, the structure of the co-spheres is more complicated. The volume contribution, ΔV , of the water molecules in the co-spheres of amino acids relative to those in bulk water would, in all probability, be the combined contribution of the following effects. (i) *Electrostriction effect*: The interaction of the zwitterionic part of the molecules with some water molecules *via* charge-dipole and hydrogen-bonding interactions will restrict water molecules in the co-sphere, giving rise to a negative ΔV . (ii) The layer of water molecules around the charged moieties, like the co-spheres of ionic species, is considered to be more disorganised (water-structure broken region) than the bulk water. This would also give rise to a negative ΔV . (iii) *Hydrophobic hydration effect*: Due to enhancement of the structure, the water molecules in the hydrophobic hydration sphere of alkyl moieties will give a positive ΔV contribution.

Overlap of urea and amino acid co-spheres may not be able to remove the electrostricted water to the bulk, since these are bound with COO⁻ and NH₃⁺ groups by strong 'charge-dipole' forces. This

presumption is supported by the conclusion of Desrosiers *et al.* that hydration numbers in the primary hydration spheres of alkali metal and halide ions do not change appreciably on transferring them to concentrated aqueous urea solutions. However, overlap of urea and amino acid co-spheres would certainly relax some water molecules from the structure-broken regions of the two molecules, resulting in an increase in volume. The overlap of the urea co-sphere with that of the hydrophobic hydration portion of the amino acid co-sphere on the other hand, would result in a decrease in volume, presumably due to a net destruction of some or all of the hydrophobic hydration co-sphere. This conjecture is also supported from the findings of Schrier *et al.* that overlap of the co-spheres of urea and Bu₄N⁺ leads to a net release of some of the water molecules from the hydrophobic hydration sphere, *i.e.* a release of the structured water to the bulk and a concomitant gain of entropy and enthalpy. These effects combined together determine the sign and magnitude of \bar{V}_{tr}° . It is apparent that the effect of the zwitterionic portion of amino acids dominates that of the alkyl side chains; accordingly, the sign of the transfer function is always positive. However, the increasing contribution of the reduction in volume due to the overlap of hydrophobic hydration co-spheres with those of urea as the side-chain length increases causes \bar{V}_{tr}° value to decrease with increasing side-chain length.

For peptides, the number of water molecules in the structure-broken region and the number of electrostricted water molecules would be greater than those in α -amino acids as a result of the separation of the charged centers COO⁻ and NH₃⁺. Furthermore, there also would be a few water molecules associated with the polar CONH group. Overlap of the co-spheres of urea with those of peptides may therefore cause of greater number of water molecules to be relaxed to the bulk, resulting in more positive \bar{V}_{tr}° values than for α -amino acids.

Solubility studies of hydrocarbons in 7 M aqueous urea solutions by Wetlaufer *et al.* and of amino acids and peptides in 6 M aqueous urea solutions by Tanford *et al.* indicate that ΔG_{tr} of the nonpolar side chains are negative (except for the alanyl side chain, which is *ca.* 10 cal mol⁻¹) and decrease with increasing alkyl chainlength. The transfer free energy of the peptide backbone unit, as the difference in ΔG_{tr} for diglycine and glycine, is *ca.* -35 cal mol⁻¹. Thus, ΔG_{tr} of residue -CONHCH(R)- would be negative for all the peptides and would decrease as the alkyl group R increased. This indicates that the interaction between the -CONHCH(R)- residue and urea increases (in the concentrated aqueous urea solution) as the side-chainlength increases. Additional support for this conclusion can be drawn from the fact that the salting-out coefficients in aqueous urea solutions decrease as the size of the alkyl chain of various solutes increases. Thus, the presence of

longer alkyl chains in higher peptides may result in a greater reinforcement of the association of the CONH group and urea molecules. Enhanced association of urea with the CONH group may ultimately produce a greater loss of water of solvation to the bulk, accompanied with a greater increase in the volume as the side-chain length increases. Such a mechanism may give rise to the observed trend of an increase in \bar{V}_r^0 of the peptides as the side-chain length increases.

Enthalpies of solution, partial molar heat capacities and apparent molar volumes of sugars and polyols in water :

Whereas, in the past many efforts have been devoted to the understanding the hydration behaviours of ionic and hydrophobic solutes, the available studies on polyfunctional hydrophilic solutes is severely limited. Because of large number of structures present in carbohydrates, these can be very good model compounds to explore the hydration behaviours of polyfunctional hydrophilic solutes. For all practical purposes, the area of carbohydrate solutions remained untouched, till Franks *et al.* took up spectroscopic and volumetric studies on sugars. They have proposed a specific hydration model, in which in addition to the number, relative positions and orientations of hydroxyl groups are also emphasised in determining hydration behaviour of a sugar.

The present investigations aim at understanding the hydration behaviours of sugars and related compounds, and exploring the possible correlation of this behaviour with the stereochemistry of a sugar molecule. For this purpose, various series of carbohydrates, *viz.* hexoses, ketoses and pentoses, were studied. Series of methylglycosides were taken to find out the effect of introduction of a non-polar group in sugar rings. The study of polyols were done with an objective of comparing the hydration behaviour of flexible acyclic structures with rigid ring structured sugars.

The thermodynamic parameters, such as enthalpy of transfer (ΔH_{tr}), heat capacity of transfer ($\Delta C_{p, tr}$) and volume of transfer (ΔV_{tr}), accompanying the transfer of a solute from water to aqueous solution are very helpful in elucidating the effect of a co-solute on hydration behaviour of the solute. An attempt has been made to explore the effect of electrolytes, such as sodium chloride and guanidine hydrochloride and a non-electrolyte, like urea, on polyhydroxy compounds (sorbitol, mannitol and some disaccharides) water interactions. Because sorbitol and mannitol show different hydration properties in water, it was thought worthwhile to see how does this difference in hydration behaviour gets altered in the presence of an electrolyte or non-electrolyte. Urea was taken up as a co-solute because of the presence in it of the functional group $-\text{CONH}-$, extensively found in protein molecules. It was thought that interactions of such groups with urea might be helpful in understanding the role of sugar moiety of glycolipid or glycoproteins present

at the periphery of the cell membranes. The integral enthalpies of solution, (ΔH_s^0), the limiting heat capacity changes (ΔC_p^0), partial molar heat capacities ($\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$) and partial molar volume (\bar{V}_s^0) of monosaccharides, deoxymonosaccharides, methyl glycosides and polyols in water are given in Tables 3 and 4. $\Delta \bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ or $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$, for all the polyhydroxy compounds studied are large and positive indicating that these polyfunctional non-electrolyte solutes act as overall water structure-promoters.

Substitution of H by OH has been shown to result in a decrease in $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ for various homologous series of alcohols, amines, carboxylic acids and amides. Similar decreases in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ have been reported for propane and its hydroxy derivatives and for amino acids. It is interesting to note that the decrease in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ and $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$, is much less for polyhydroxy compounds. This indicates that the $\Delta \bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ and $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$, contribution from the hydroxyl groups in these molecules is higher than that in predominantly apolar solutes. This is further supported by the observation that the $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$, for polyhydroxy compounds calculated using groups contribution for constituent groups (obtained by using additivity relations in predominantly apolar solutes) are lower than the experimentally observed $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$.

The high heat capacity observed in such compounds can be attributed to stronger or more extensive hydrogen bonding between solute hydroxyl groups and water molecules. Similar conclusions have been drawn by others from spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies. The stronger or more extensive hydrogen bonding between polyhydroxy non-electrolytes and water has been explained in terms of a specific hydration model. In sugars, the equatorial hydroxyl oxygens on the same side of the pyranose ring in the C1 chain conformation are 4.82 Å apart. This distance corresponds to the second nearest neighbour oxygen distance in water. X-Ray diffraction studies also indicate a high concentration of water molecules at 4.9 Å part. This concept of compatibility of sugar structure with tetrahedral structure of water has been involved by various researchers and our volume studies are also consistent with that view. From Tables 3 and 4, it can be seen that the effect on \bar{V}_s^0 of substitution of H by OH in the corresponding monohydric alcohols or hydrocarbons to obtain sugars or polyols is negligible confirming that there is little perturbation in water structure on hydroxyl group substitution.

Franks *et al.*, from their partial molar volume studies have pointed out that the β -hydroxyl of sugars is more hydrated than the α -hydroxyl group. Our results on partial molar volumes of various anomers do not show such a pattern. Also, $\Delta \bar{C}_{p, s}^0$ or $\bar{C}_{p, s}^0$, results for α , β -glucose and a series of methylglycosides do not show any difference for the two anomers. From our results it would appear that a change of orientation of the OH or OCH₂ group from α to β does not result in any change in limiting

TABLE 3—STANDARD THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR MONOSACCHARIDES AND THEIR DEOXYDERIVATIVES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION*

Compd.	ΔH_f°		ΔC_p°	$C_{p,s}^\circ$ 30°	$\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$	\bar{V}_s° 25°	
	25°	35°					
α -D-Glucose	10.70 ± 0.04 10.79 11.04 ± 0.04	12.04 ± 0.12	184 ± 12	223	357 251 ^e 326 ^f 331 ^d	111.7 111.9, 111.5	112.2 ± 0.04
β -D-Glucose	4.42 ± 0.07 4.70 4.54 ± 0.27	5.70 ± 0.07	128 ± 10	223	351	111.72	
D-Galactose	17.20 ± 0.10	18.55 ± 0.09	189 ± 14	217	356 324 ^e	110.64 110.7	111.9 ± 0.8
D-Mannose	6.86 ± 0.06	8.84 ± 0.09	148 ± 11	215	368 337 ^d	111.96	111.7 ± 0.3
D-Fructose	8.80 ± 0.10	11.20 ± 0.09	242 ± 18	238	475 352 ^d	110.88	110.4 ± 0.4
L-Sorbose	6.94 ± 0.03	9.11 ± 0.05	217 ± 6	233	450	111.54	110.6 ± 0.4
D-Arabinose	18.24 ± 0.06	14.58 ± 0.10	184 ± 12	184	318	94.00	
D-Xylose	11.98 ± 0.05	12.95 ± 0.07	97 ± 8	184	281	95.60	94.8 ± 0.4
L-Xylose	12.19 ± 0.08	13.25 ± 0.10	108 ± 12	184	291	95.59	
D-Lyxose	10.10 ± 0.01	11.11 ± 0.11	101 ± 12	184	285	95.69	
D-Ribose	18.04 ± 0.14	14.14 ± 0.09	110 ± 15	184	294	95.56	95.3
2-Deoxy-D-glucose	9.43 ± 0.06	11.23 ± 0.15	180 ± 16	201	331	110.4 ± 0.5	
2-Deoxy-D-galactose	10.91 ± 0.10	12.70 ± 0.17	180 ± 10	201	336		
6-Deoxy-D-galactose	1.97 ± 0.10	3.90 ± 0.07	193 ± 12	201	334		
2-Deoxy-D-ribose	10.73 ± 0.13	12.39 ± 0.09	169 ± 12	164	333	93.8 ± 0.4	

* Ref. 80, units for ΔH_f° , kJ mol⁻¹, for heat capacities, JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, for volumes, cm³ mol⁻¹.

TABLE 4—STANDARD THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF POLYOLS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION*

Compd.	ΔH_f°		ΔC_p°	$C_{p,s}^\circ$ 30°	$\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$	\bar{V}_s° 25°
	25°	35°				
D-Sorbitol	16.86 ± 0.07	18.18 ± 0.05	194 ± 8	230	424 (428)	119.26 (119.16) (118.2 ± 0.3) (119.33)
D-Mannitol	21.54 ± 0.09 (22.54 ± 0.21)	23.86 ± 0.04	232 ± 9	229	461 (455)	119.53 (119.71) (118.6)
D-Galactitol	22.22 ± 0.12 (22.67)	21.98 ± 0.10	216 ± 16	229	445	
D-Arabitol	18.71 ± 0.08	20.30 ± 0.07	159 ± 8	192	351 (375)	(108.31)
D-Ribitol	18.55 ± 0.06	20.17 ± 0.10	162 ± 12	192	354 (376)	(108.11)
D-Xylitol	22.40 ± 0.012	23.74 ± 0.14	134 ± 9	192	326 (346)	(100.1 ± 0.3)
Meso-erythritol	22.38 ± 0.08 (23.31 ± 0.04)	23.61 ± 0.13	124 ± 21	152	276 (310)	(87.10)
Penta-erythritol	22.02 ± 0.12	23.31 ± 0.16	129 ± 17	172	301 (323)	(86.7 ± 0.4)
Myo-inositol	14.98 ± 0.12	16.46 ± 0.04	148 ± 13	221		

* Explanations as Table 3.

thermodynamic properties. However, this observation is not consistent with the compatibility concept invoked earlier.

Furthermore ΔC_p° and $\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$ for stereoisomers, within a particular series of compounds are the same (the small difference falling within experimental error) indicating similar hydration behaviour for the two stereoisomers. Similar observations for glucose, mannose and galactose have been made by others from spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies. 1-O-Methylglucopyranoside has the same

ΔC_p° or $\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$ as 3-O-methyl-glucopyranoside and 2-deoxy-D-glucose the same as 6-deoxy-D-glucose. It appears, therefore, that the position of the OCH₃ or CH₂ groups does not affect the mode or extent of hydration.

The compounds with the 1C-pyranose chain conformation in the crystalline state appear to have higher $\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$ than those with 1C-pyranose chain conformation, e.g. the $\bar{C}_{p,s}^\circ$ for D-arabinose with 1C-structure is larger than that for its stereoisomers with 1C-structure. It can not be said, at the

moment, that the higher heat capacity for L-sorbose in comparison to that for D-glucose is due to the difference in the conformation (1C and 1C) or due to functional groups. However, Kawaizumi has also reported higher $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ for fructose.

The D- and L-stereoisomers do not show any difference in the limiting thermodynamic properties as seen for D-xylose and L-xylose both having the same ΔC_p° and \bar{V}_2° . Similar conclusions have been drawn from thermodynamic studies of D- and L-arabitol.

Comparison of the results in Table 4 shows that the substitution of OH by OCH_3 results in an increase of about $66 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in ΔC_p° , $76 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ and $20 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in \bar{V}_2° . The increase in ΔC_p° agrees with the value obtained for CH_3 addition in predominantly apolar compounds. But the changes in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ ($76 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) is less than that observed in apolar solutes ($88 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicating that the change in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ accompanying CH_3 addition in polyhydroxy compounds is lower by about $12 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ than that observed in hydrophobic solutes. Comparison of $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ for alkoxy ethanols and dialkoxy ethanes also shows that for the OH to CH_3 group substitution, the change in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ is $7-18 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ less than that accompanying CH_3 addition in predominantly apolar solutes. In predominantly apolar solutes, the addition of CHO group results in either a decrease or no change in the heat capacity whereas the partial molar volume increases by $16-18 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Similar volume changes ($15-18 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) per CHO addition are observed in polyhydroxy solutes but the heat capacities show an increase. This increase in heat capacities reflects the positive contribution of the OH group towards heat capacity in such solutes.

Within the polyol series, mannitol and galactitol have higher heat capacities than sorbitol. Also, arabitol and ribitol are higher than xylitol. These differences have been explained by Dipaola and Belleau in terms of compatibility between polyol conformation and water structure. Nmr studies show that sorbitol, xylitol, and ribitol possess non-planar sickle conformation in aqueous solution, whereas all other polyols mentioned above have planar zigzag conformation. With ribitol as an exception, it can be seen that a planar zigzag structure, being more compatible with the water structure, shows higher ΔC_p° or $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ than a non-planar structure.

In this context, Warner, from his model building studies, pointed out that in many biological molecules, the spacing of ether, ester, hydroxyl and carbonyl oxygen atoms is about 4.8 \AA , which is very close to the next nearest oxygen spacing in a hypothetical ice I lattice at 298 K (4.75 \AA). This suggests that provided there exists in liquid water some resemblance to an 'ice-like' structure, mole-

cules like biotin, 1,4-quinone, β -D-glucose and triglycerides (Fig. 18) could be cooperatively hydrogen bonded into water structure without undue modification of the existing hydrogen bonded system.

In the light of 'flickering cluster' model, one can say that the above mentioned solute structures are more compatible with $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ component and thereby might shift the equilibrium to the side of structured propensity.

Fig. 18. Correlation between oxygen spacings in organic molecules and in the ice lattice. Numbers in the formulae indicate interaction points with the correspondingly numbered oxygens in the ice lattice (Ref. 58).

Di-, tri-, and tetra-saccharides⁵¹ :

Like monosaccharides and their derivatives $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ as well as ΔC_p° of the di-, tri-, and tetra-saccharides show large positive values (Table 5). Partial molar heat capacities $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ (est) were also estimated using an additivity relation and heat capacities for constituent groups derived from the heat capacities of monofunctional compounds. Comparison of experimentally observed and estimated $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ (Table 5) indicates that the additivity relation does not hold good for these compounds. We have also calculated the difference in $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ (expt) and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ (est) per OH group in di-, tri-, and tetra-saccharides. These quantities alongwith those on monosaccharides, *i.e.* for pentoses (24 to $27 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and for hexoses (27 to $32 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), reflect that this difference per OH group also increases with an increase in number of hydroxyl groups in a molecule. Similar increase was also observed in the polyol series, namely, pentitols (5 to $11 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and hexitols

TABLE 5—EXPERIMENTAL AND ESTIMATED PARTIAL MOLAR HEAT CAPACITIES OF DI-, TRI-, AND TETRA-SACCHARIDES IN WATER

Compd.	$C_{p,2}^{\circ}/(J K^{-1} mol^{-1})$		$\Delta C_{p,2}^{\circ}$ $J K^{-1} mol^{-1}$	No. n of OH groups	$\Delta C_{p,2}^{\circ}/n$ $J K^{-1} mol^{-1}$
	expt	est. ^a			
Sucrose	647	281	386	8	46
Maltose	635	281	354	8	44
Lactose	673	281	392	8	49
Trehalose	656	281	375	8	47
Melibiose	649	281	368	8	46
Turanose	666	281	385	8	48
Raffinose	978	381	597	11	54
Stachyose	1 265	519	746	14	58

^a $C_{p,2}^{\circ}$'s were estimated using $C_{p,2}^{\circ}$ for various constituent groups of the molecule as reported in Ref. 80.

(15 to 21 $J K^{-1} mol^{-1}$). However, there is a sharp increase as one goes from mono- to di-saccharides. This might indicate some cooperative effect. The near constancy of $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ per OH after tri-saccharides shows that this $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ per OH group may be a better value than that obtained from monofunctional compounds for estimating $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ of a polysaccharide. However, study of some more oligosaccharides is needed to substantiate this view.

$\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ and ΔC_p° for sucrose and maltose are lower than those of their stereoisomer lactose. Also maltose monohydrate possesses a lower $\bar{C}_{p,2}^{\circ}$ than lactose monohydrate. The smaller heat capacity of sucrose and maltose monohydrate compared with their respective stereoisomers can be attributed to their folded or distorted conformations in aqueous solutions reported from nmr and other studies. The distorted or folded structures of these compounds may not be as compatible with the tetrahedral water structure as the planar conformation of lactose. However, a detailed study of conformations of sugars in aqueous solution is required to arrive at definite conclusions.

Thermodynamics of transfer of sorbitol and mannitol from water to aqueous solutions of urea, guanidine hydrochloride and sodium chloride^{82,83}:

A few studies have shown that sorbitol and mannitol, despite their structural similarity, have different hydration properties. For example, it has been reported that these compounds show a real difference in the osmotic pressure coefficients in measurements up to 1 mol dm⁻³. Wilson and Wen, from a study of enthalpies of sodium chloride from water to aqueous solutions of polyols, inferred that sorbitol is a relatively stronger disruptor of the solvent structure than mannitol. Heat capacity and volume studies have also shown that mannitol behaves differently from sorbitol as far as hydration is concerned. It will be interesting to see how this difference in the hydration behaviour of sorbitol and mannitol is modified in the presence of an electrolyte or non-electrolyte co-solute in the solution.

It is well known that the extent of denaturation of certain proteins by urea-type denaturants is

reduced in the presence of sugars or polyhydroxy alcohols. However, whether this renaturing effect on protein structures is due to the direct binding of urea with the polyhydroxy compound/protein molecules or is due to the alteration of water structure is not known. It was thought that the transfer of polyhydroxy alcohols from water to aqueous urea solution might shed some light on urea-polyhydroxy-alcohol interactions.

With these objectives, a thermodynamic study of the transfer of sorbitol and mannitol from water to aqueous solutions of urea and guanidine hydrochloride was taken up. To compare the effect of urea and guanidine hydrochloride with that of an electrolyte, transfer studies were also carried out in aqueous sodium chloride solutions. Thermodynamic parameters determined include enthalpy of transfer, heat capacity of transfer and volume of transfer.

Enthalpies of transfer: Both sorbitol and mannitol show negative enthalpies of transfer at all concentrations of urea (Fig. 19), and the negative enthalpy of transfer increases in magnitude with increasing urea concentration. It may also be noted that the enthalpy of transfer for sorbitol is more negative than that of mannitol at all concentrations of urea. No direct calorimetric study of the transfer of a hydrophilic non-electrolyte from water to aqueous urea solution could be traced in the literature. However, the enthalpies of transfer of a peptide unit (CONH) or peptide backbone (CH₂CONH), which have potential hydrogen-bonding sites similar to the hydroxyl groups of sorbitol and mannitol, have been reported by some workers. In these groups, negative enthalpies of transfer, which become more negative at higher concentrations of urea, were also observed. The enthalpy of transfer behaviour for sorbitol and mannitol from water to aqueous urea solution is seen to contrast with that of hydrophobic solutes (which show positive enthalpies of transfer) but is similar to that of ionic hydrophilic solutes (which show negative enthalpies of transfer).

The positive enthalpies of transfer from water to aqueous urea solution for hydrophobic solutes and negative enthalpies of transfer for ionic hydrophilic solutes have been rationalised in terms of the struc-

Fig. 19. Enthalpies of transfer of sorbitol (closed symbols) and mannitol (open symbols) from water to various mixed aqueous solutions at 298.15 K: (○, ●) water→water—NaCl, (□, ■) water→water—guanidine hydrochloride, (△, ▲) water→water—urea.

ture-breaking effect of urea molecules. However, it appears that the behaviour of hydrophilic non-electrolytes can be best accounted for in terms of solute—co-solute interactions. The negative enthalpies of transfer for sorbitol and mannitol seem to result from interactions between urea and polyol molecules. The most probable interaction appears to be formation of a hydrogen-bonding complex, since both urea and polyols possess potential sites for hydrogen bonding. According to this view, the magnitude of exothermicity should increase with increasing urea concentration, which is indeed the case. The idea of complex formation between a carboxylic/peptide group and urea molecules to explain the exothermic enthalpies of transfer for some amino acid/peptide groups has been invoked before. The difference in magnitude of ΔH_{tr} for sorbitol and mannitol can be explained in terms of the difference in their compatibility with the tetrahedral order in water as reflected in their different heat capacity values in water. Mannitol, due to its planar zigzag conformation in aqueous solution, is expected to fit better into the tetrahedral water structure than sorbitol with its sickle-bent structure. Consequently, the availability of mannitol molecules for hydrogen bonding to urea is less than that of sorbitol molecules. Thus the larger exothermicity observed for sorbitol may result from more extensive interactions of sorbitol and urea molecules. These observations are consistent with the compatibility concept used to explain the difference in hydration properties of sorbitol and mannitol. Planar mannitol is more compatible with the water structure than non-planar sorbitol. As a result, the hydroxyl

groups of mannitol are less free for interactions with co-solute sodium chloride molecules. If the enthalpy of transfer is taken as a combination of the contributions of non-polar CH_2 and polar OH groups, it appears that for mannitol the contribution of non-polar groups (positive ΔH_{tr} outweighs the contribution of polar hydroxyl groups (negative ΔH_{tr}), thus resulting in positive enthalpies of transfer.

Whereas sorbitol exhibits exothermic behaviour on transferring from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride, mannitol exhibits endothermicity. Negative enthalpies of transfer from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride are also reported for a polar backbone unit (CH_2CONH) by Lapanje *et al.* and Stimson and Schrier. Fig. 19 shows that the behaviour of polyols in guanidine hydrochloride is intermediate between that of urea and sodium chloride. This is not surprising, since guanidine hydrochloride, in addition to having some of the structural features of urea, also possesses the ionic character of an electrolyte, like sodium chloride. The difference in enthalpies of transfer of sorbitol and mannitol can also be explained in terms of their interactions with guanidinium hydrochloride molecules and their compatibility with the water structure.

Heat capacities of transfer : Our results on heat capacities of transfer from water to aqueous urea solutions show positive ΔC_{ptr} , both for sorbitol and mannitol. The heat capacity changes accompanying the transfer of various groups (*viz.* CONH and CH_2CONH) having potential hydrogen-bonding sites from water to aqueous urea solution have also been shown to be positive. Ionic solutes like alkali-metal halides also show increased heat capacity values when transferred from water to aqueous urea solutions. However, it has been observed that the heat capacities of hydrophobic solutes decrease on transferring from water to aqueous urea solutions.

Polyols behave in a manner similar to ionic hydrophilic groups as far as their heat capacity of transfer is concerned. But positive ΔC_{ptr} values in the case of sorbitol and mannitol might result from complex formation between urea and polyols, probably through hydrogen bonding. Similar conclusions were reached in our enthalpy studies. Other workers have also used the idea of complex formation between urea and COOH/CONH groups to explain the positive ΔC_{ptr} from water to aqueous urea solution. However, heat capacities observed in polyols are much smaller in magnitude than those observed in the case of COOH or CONH groups. This reflects the weaker or smaller interactions in the case of polyols. Polyols, according to the specific hydration model, are strongly/extensively bound with water molecules. Thus their interactions with urea molecules are expected to be smaller than peptide or amino acids which might not have any specific interactions with water. ΔC_{ptr} of

sorbitol and mannitol from water to aqueous sodium chloride solutions is almost zero for sorbitol, whereas mannitol exhibits a significantly positive ΔC_{DTR} value. These observations are in agreement with the view that in mannitol the contribution of non-polar CH_2 groups towards ΔC_{DTR} outweighs the contribution of the OH groups. However, in sorbitol the situation is different because of the comparatively free availability of hydroxyl groups.

In the case of guanidine hydrochloride solutions, due to the small changes, it is difficult to draw conclusions from the heat capacity of transfer data alone. However, it is certain that unlike hydrophobic solutes, heat capacities do not decrease on transferring polyols from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions. This suggests the possibility of the existence of interactions between polyols and guanidine hydrochloride molecules.

Volumes of transfer: Transfer from water to aqueous urea solution both for sorbitol and mannitol (Figs. 20 and 21) is accompanied by positive volume changes. Sangster *et al.* have also reported an increase in the partial molar volume of sucrose when it is transferred from water to aqueous urea solutions. It has been shown that the transfer of hydrophobic and ionic solutes from water to aqueous urea solution also exhibits positive volumes of transfer.

The structure-breaking effect of urea in aqueous solution has been used to explain the positive volumes of transfer from water to aqueous urea solutions for hydrophobic as well as ionic solutes. In the case of polyhydroxy compounds like sorbitol and mannitol, it appears, especially in the light of heat capacity and enthalpy data, that interactions of these molecules with urea also contribute to volume changes. It has been pointed out by

Fig. 20. Volumes of transfer of mannitol from water to aqueous solutions of urea (Δ), guanidine hydrochloride (\square), and sodium chloride (\circ) at 298.15 K.

Fig. 21. Volumes of transfer of sorbitol from water to aqueous solutions of urea (Δ), guanidine hydrochloride (\square), and sodium chloride (\circ) at 298.15 K.

Franks *et al.* that the partial molar volume of non-electrolyte is a combination of two factors, viz. the intrinsic volume of the solute and the volume due to its interactions with solvent. Some investigators have approximated the intrinsic volume as

$$V_{\text{intrinsic}} = V_{\text{vw}} + V_{\text{void}}$$

where, V_{vw} is the van der Waals volume and V_{void} is the associated void or empty volume. Shahidi *et al.* have modified this equation to find the contribution of one molecule towards the partial molar volume of a hydrophilic non-electrolyte solute as

$$\bar{V}^{\circ} = V_{\text{vw}} + V_{\text{void}} - n\sigma_s$$

where, σ_s is the shrinkage in volume caused by interactions of a hydrogen-bonding group with water molecules and n is the number of potential hydrogen-bonding sites in a molecules. Thus the partial molar volume of a sugar or polyol molecule can be represented as

$$\bar{V} = V_{\text{vw}} + V_{\text{void}} - V_{\text{shrinkage}}$$

If one assumes that V_{vw} and V_{void} have the same magnitudes in water and aqueous urea solution, the positive volume change accompanying the transfer of sorbitol and mannitol might arise from the decrease in $V_{\text{shrinkage}}$ in urea solution. Because of the interactions of the polyol hydroxyl groups with urea molecules, the effect of hydroxyl groups on water structure is decreased, thus causing a decrease in $V_{\text{shrinkage}}$. Furthermore, the interactions of urea with polyols also result in urea having a reduced structure-breaking effect on water. In other words, more water is released as bulk water in the presence of polyol. Since bulk water has higher volume contributions than structure-broken water, this factor may also be contributing to the positive volume changes (Figs. 17 and 21) observed in our study. The higher magnitude of ΔV_{tr} observed in sorbitol might be a reflection of the stronger interaction of

sorbitol with urea. Volumes of transfer from water to aqueous sodium chloride/aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solution for sorbitol and mannitol also show positive values. It appears that in these cases, too, the positive ΔV_{tr} results from the decreased effect of co-solute and solute on water structure which arises due to solute-co-solute interactions as mentioned earlier.

The thermodynamic parameters (*viz.* enthalpy, heat capacity and volume) accompanying the transfer of sorbitol and mannitol from water to aqueous urea, guanidine hydrochloride and sodium chloride point toward the possibility of interactions between hydroxyl groups or polyols and co-solute molecules. The difference in the magnitude of the thermodynamic transfer functions supports the view that the planar conformation of mannitol is more compatible with the tetrahedral water structure than the non-planar conformation of sorbitol.

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